

RESEARCH OF UZBEK ORNITHONYMS AND ITS MAIN DIRECTION.

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One of the peculiarities of Uzbek ornithonymy is that in our national heritage of birds, in the study of the world of birds, works that are not specifically dedicated to birds or whose names are not related to birds have a large place. For example, some of the incidents related to the birds and flight of Sufism are also included in Alisher Navoi's work "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat". We will pay attention to some pictures from it that are directly related to the topic. In the work, people did not accept the famous Zunnun Misri ideas, the leech for life. But "Zunnun has passed away as a saint." . In the morning of the funeral, the green birds overshadowed the funeral. And so, a large number of people were in their shoes. After Andin, Zunnunga became accepted in the hearts of the people" (!) Alisher Navoi writes during these words, "After the end of the term, birds shadowed the funeral of Shafi'i's student Mu'azzini." So these words show that there is truth behind the ancient view of birds as mediators with the divine realm. At the same time, we will also learn that in Islamic beliefs, birds are considered a special symbol. In Sufism, flight is distinguished by having a certain meaning, even if it is not considered a separate status and destination. The flight of the Sufi is a special virtue of the Truth and should serve for spiritual perfection. That's why Sufi Oloyor says, "If a person without Shariat flies, don't worry about self-righteousness." In Nasoyim ul-Muhabbat, Alisher Navoi tells Jalaluddin Rumi, when he was six years old, while playing with children on Friday night, "Let's jump to another roof from this roof." Then the young Muhammad (Jalaluddin Balkhi) said, "This action is a dog and cat affair!" If you have the energy in your soul, let's jump to the roof of the sky!" – in this case Tomdin rises into the air. Then the children will cry. After a moment, young Jalaluddin returned to the same roof, his eyes and color changed. To the children, "I told you the same word that the green ones took me up to heaven and showed me the wonder of the kingdom. When your screams and cries came out, they brought you down here again." Fariduddin Attar, speaking to his murids about the purpose and actions of dervishes, compares the tax to a bird, that is, a dervish is a bird, and even if it cannot fly in the sky, it will at least rise above the roof: "A bird will fly above the

earth, if it does not reach the sky, but be far from the sky. Hamul nav' if a person is a dervish, if the dervish is not perfected, but let it be such that he is a classic of folk religion and bazaar people and successful in the world's toils. I went there before and saw when he was praying, green and white birds were praying in the sky with us. When we finished the prayer, a green bird came among the birds and killed it near the coffin, swallowed the coffin and flew away to join the other birds. And they recited the tasbih and disappeared from sight. I was surprised. That person said: O Umar, have you not heard that the souls of martyrs will be in the green birds that roam in any land of paradise. These are those who were martyred by the sword. But the bodies and souls of martyrs of love will be in green birds. This person is one of them, O Umar! The Sheikh said that three days after my death, the citizens will gather, and if a green bird comes and kills everyone, kill it instead of me! Three days after the Sheikh's death, when the citizens were gathering, a green bird came,

Maqam - address, stage, spiritual position, career, stop. According to Najmuddin Kubro, "the position is to get rid of traffic congestion is to relax and entertain. Status is the two wings of a bird, and status is its nest.

There was one problem. When we saw Luqman, he immediately flew to us and told us about the matter. And that's it, the work has stopped. He flew again and came out of the room. Perhaps, from the point of view of loftiness, Sheikh Luqmon was given the name of poultry. In the Uzbek classical heritage, some historical ornithonymy plays an important role. For example, in the work "Shajarai tarokima" Abulghozi Bahadirkhan writes in the chapter "Meanings of the horses and marks and birds of Oguz Khan's grandsons": I will tell you,..” – notes the following: "The meaning of birch is mahkam temak, the bird is shunqar" Shunqor is a general name used for all falcon-type birds in Eastern Turkestan. In Anatolia, this bird is usually called sungur. In the Kyrgyz language, the word sumkar is a name used for all birds of the falcon and hawk family. In this way, the meaning, symbol and bird of the name of each clan are given in the work: "The meaning of Bayot is a stately temak, the bird is uki (ukki); The meaning of alka evli is a suitable match. ... the bird is kukanik; The meaning of black marriage is that if you kill a bird, it will be a sledgehammer, ... The meaning of summer is that the country's water will be warm, ... the bird will rise; Yasir's meaning is that if anything comes in front of him, it will be a yiqar temak, ... the bird is cursing; The meaning of a stutter is a tree that knows how to be a country and how to preserve it, ... the bird is a red sparrow; The meaning of dukar is tosarak (Turkish) temak, ...

the bird has migrated (kochkin); The meaning of Avshar is to work hard, ... the bird is a falcon; The meaning of "fun" is "boka temak", ... like a bird; The meaning of Bekdili is the word respectable, ... the sea of birds; The meaning of "Qarqin" is "Oshly temak", ... the bird is humoy; The meaning of "salur" is a falcon, ... the bird is a falcon; The meaning of "Bajna" is "The bird is a bird". The meaning of chavuldur is a dish of honor, ...the bird is like wheat; The meaning of chebni (jebni) is price is temak, ... the bird is humoy; The meaning of Aymir is the wealth of the rich. The meaning of ola yontli is ola otli temak, ... the bird is fat; The meaning of Uragir is a doer of good deeds, a bird is a bird; The meaning of Igdir is a great tree, ... the bird is a bird; The meaning of Bukdur is a servant temak, ... the bird is italgu; The meaning of Ava (Iva) is that the career is high, the bird is feeling; The meaning of the guest is a dear temak, ... the bird is a bird of prey. B. Ozel gives exactly this information in his book.